

EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES AND FOOD SECURITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Agriculture is a critical sector in Nigeria, employing over 70% of the population and contributing significantly to the nation's GDP. However, climate change poses a severe threat to agricultural productivity and food security. Rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, desertification, and extreme weather events disrupt farming activities, leading to reduced crop yields, increased food prices, and heightened food insecurity. This paper examines the multifaceted impacts of climate change on Nigeria's agricultural sector, highlighting how changing climatic conditions exacerbate vulnerabilities in food production, distribution, and accessibility. The study explores key challenges such as reduced agricultural output, disruptions in food supply chains, increased pest invasions, and the socio-economic implications of climate change on smallholder farmers. It also assesses governmental policies, adaptation strategies, and international collaborations aimed at mitigating these adverse effects. Despite efforts such as the National Climate Change Policy and the Agricultural Transformation Agenda, implementation gaps persist due to inadequate funding, limited technological adoption, and socio-cultural barriers. A comparative analysis with other nations underscores the need for Nigeria to adopt sustainable agricultural practices, improve climate resilience through research and innovation, and enhance policy execution. The paper concludes that addressing food security challenges necessitates a comprehensive approach involving governmental action, stakeholder collaboration, and increased investments in climate-smart agriculture to build a more resilient food system in Nigeria.*

Introduction

Agriculture is a key sector in Nigeria, employing over 70% of the population and contributing significantly to the country's GDP (FAO, 2021).

However, climate change poses a serious threat to agricultural productivity and food security. Rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, desertification, and extreme weather events are

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disrupting farming activities and reducing crop yields. This paper examines these effects and their implications for Nigeria's food security.

Climate change could potentially interrupt progress toward a world without hunger. A robust and coherent global pattern is discernible in the impacts of climate change on crop productivity that could have consequences for food availability. The stability of whole food systems may be at risk under climate change because of short-term variability in supply. However, the potential impact is less clear at regional scales, but climate variability and change will likely exacerbate food insecurity in areas currently vulnerable to hunger and under-nutrition. Likewise, it can be anticipated that food access and utilization will be affected indirectly via collateral effects on household incomes, and food utilization could be impaired by loss of access to drinking water and damage to health. The evidence supports the need for considerable investment in adaptation and mitigation actions toward a "climate-smart food system" that is more resilient to climate change influences on food security (T. Wheeler et al).

Food security, like climate change, is a multifaceted issue. It is affected not only by obvious influences such as climate and weather but also by oil and commodity prices, trade and social policies, global politics, and population growth, to name just a few (Gamble, Sussman, & Wilbanks, 2021). Combining the two to determine how climate change may impact food security is complex.

Climate encompasses the statistics of temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind, precipitation, atmospheric particle count and other meteorological elemental measurements in a given region over long periods. Climate change is the drastic alteration in natural components of the atmospheric environment, with the resultant adverse responses such as the shift in weather variations or patterns involving overall and unprecedented changes in weather patterns, which may include unusual rain yield or precipitation temperature, density, or cloud look (Karl, Melillo, & Peterson, 2019). Climate change is caused by factors that include oceanic processes (such as oceanic circulation), biotic processes, and variation in solar radiation received by Earth, plate tectonics, volcanic eruptions, and human-induced alteration of the natural world. These latter effects are currently causing global warming (causing defrosting of ice in the Arctic and Antarctic regions), and "climate change" is often greatly and mostly caused by human-specific impacts.

The public has also been blamed for their contribution to climate change, which is affecting Food Security in Nigeria. In the bid to meet our energy needs, Nigerians over-depend on the use of fossil fuels, which release toxic gases like greenhouse gases (GHGs), mainly carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane, into the atmosphere. Fertilizers used in our farms to improve crop yield are also petrochemical products, which also affect the atmosphere negatively. Excess fertilizer escapes from fields as gases into the

atmosphere. The use of synthetic nitrogen fertilizer has accelerated the increase in nitrous oxide in the last few decades. Other farming and lumbering activities like tree felling and bush burning lead to deforestation and the resultant emission of CO₂, which saturates the earth's atmosphere and consequently results in thicker cloud layers with adverse consequences on climatic weather conditions. When all these occur, the result is an increase in temperature and rainfall variation (resulting in drought and desertification in some regions and some parts flooding). All these have been threatening Food Security in Nigeria and need the urgent attention of the Nigerian government and populace.

Food Security: It is generally accepted that the term 'food security' means, in simplest terms, "access to nutritious food." Food security, as defined by the FAO, comprises availability, access, utilization, and stability. Climate change negatively impacts all these dimensions in Nigeria.

- **Reduced Agricultural Output:** Declining crop and livestock yields due to climate stressors have significantly impacted food availability. According to Nwafor (2021), Nigeria faces a decline in per capita food production, leading to higher food prices and reduced affordability for low-income households.

- **Increased Food Prices:** As agricultural productivity declines, the cost of food surges, making it difficult for many Nigerians to afford nutritious meals. Inflation in food prices exacerbates malnutrition, particularly among children and pregnant women (Eze et al., 2020).

- **Disruptions in Food Distribution:** Extreme weather events such as floods and droughts disrupt transportation and storage facilities, limiting food distribution. Flooding in states like Benue and Kogi often washes away farmlands and stored food reserves (Adeola & Agbaje, 2021)

Overall Effects of Climate Change on Food Security

Food insecurity is the single greatest danger of climate change to vulnerable human populations and indeed to all humanity. Understanding the specific impacts of climate change on food security is challenging because vulnerabilities are unevenly spread across the world and ultimately depend on the ability of communities and countries to cope with risks. In the context of food security, some regions of the world might experience gains under climate change, but developing countries are likely to be negatively affected. That is because there are multiple adverse impacts of global warming and climate disruption on agriculture, and all of these impacts will increase as the global temperature increases. Climate-related threats to global food production include risks to grain, vegetable, and fruit crops, livestock, and fisheries (Karl, Melillo, & Peterson, 2019).

- **Reduced yields:** The productivity of crops and livestock, including milk yields, may decline because of high temperatures and drought-related stress.

- **Increased irrigation:** Regions of the world that now depend on rain-fed agriculture

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may require irrigation, bringing higher costs and conflict over access to water.

- **Planting and harvesting changes:** Shifting seasonal rainfall patterns and more severe precipitation events, and related flooding, may delay planting and harvesting.

- **Decreased arability:** Prime growing temperatures may shift to higher latitudes, where soil and nutrients may not be as suitable for producing crops, leaving lower-latitude areas less productive.

- **More pests:** Insect and plant pests may survive or even reproduce more often each year if cold winters no longer keep them in check. New pests may also invade each region as temperature and humidity conditions change. Lower-latitude pests may move to higher latitudes, for example.

- **Risks to fisheries:** Shifts in the abundance and types of fish and other seafood may hurt commercial fisheries, while warmer waters may pose threats to human consumption, such as increasing the risk of infectious diseases. Extreme ocean temperatures and ocean acidification place coral reefs, the foundations of many of the world's fisheries at risk.

- **Impact on Crops:** Trying to understand the overall effect of climate change on our food

supply can be difficult. Increases in temperature and carbon dioxide (CO₂) can be beneficial for some crops in some places. But to realize these benefits, nutrient levels, soil moisture, water availability, and other conditions must also be met. Changes in the frequency and severity of droughts and floods could pose challenges for farmers and ranchers.

In some areas, warming may benefit the types of crops that are typically planted there. However, if warming exceeds a crop's optimum temperature, yields can decline.

Higher CO₂ levels can increase yields. The yields for some crops, like wheat and soybeans, could increase by 30% or more under a doubling of CO₂ concentrations (Karl, Melillo, & Peterson, 2019). The yields for other crops, such as corn, exhibit a much smaller response (less than 10% increase)

However, some factors may counteract these potential increases in yield. For example, if temperature exceeds a crop's optimal level or if sufficient water and nutrients are not available, yield increases may be reduced or reversed. More extreme temperatures and precipitation can prevent crops from growing. Extreme events, especially floods and droughts, can harm crops and reduce yields.

Fig 1: Flood-affected newly transplanted rice farm

Fig. 2: Flooded Rice farm

Fig. 3: Drought-affected Corn farm

Fig. 4: Drought-Affected Guinea corn farm
Many weeds, pests, and fungi thrive under warmer temperatures, wetter climates, and increased CO₂ levels. Currently, farmers spend more than \$11 billion per year to fight weeds in the United States. The ranges of weeds and pests

are likely to expand northward. This would cause new problems for farmers' crops previously unexposed to these species. Moreover, increased use of pesticides and fungicides may negatively affect human health (Gamble, Sussman, & Wilbanks, 2021).

Fig. 5: Drought-affected land

Fig. 6: Flooded settlements

Impact on Livestock

Climate change could affect animals both directly and indirectly. Heat waves, which are projected to increase with climate change, could directly threaten livestock. A number of states have each reported losses of more than 5,000 animals from just one heat wave (Karl, Melillo, & Peterson, 2019). Heat stress affects animals both directly and indirectly. Over time, heat stress can increase vulnerability to disease, reduce fertility, and reduce milk production. Drought may

threaten pasture and feed supplies. Drought reduces the amount of quality forage available to grazing livestock. Some areas could experience longer, more intense droughts, resulting from higher summer temperatures and reduced precipitation. For animals that rely on grain, changes in crop production due to drought could also become a problem. Climate change may increase the prevalence of parasites and diseases that affect livestock. The earlier onset of spring

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and warmer winters could allow some parasites and pathogens to survive more easily.

Increases in carbon dioxide (CO₂) may increase the productivity of pastures, but may also decrease their quality. Increases in atmospheric CO₂ can increase the productivity of plants for livestock feed. However, studies indicate that the

quality of some of the forage found in pasturelands decreases with higher CO₂. As a result, cattle would need to eat more to get the same nutritional benefits. Floods, in most cases, have been found to reduce the grazing land and hence the quantity of grass for the cattle.

Fig. 7: Flooded Cattle Ranch

What Does Climate Change Mean For Food Security At The Urban-Scale?

At the urban scale, reduced food production, especially of staple food crops, means reduced (or unstable) food supplies and food unavailability. While imports (other distribution mechanisms and safety nets) can potentially and partially cover such food gaps, evidence from across the country abounds on the ineptitude of some governments in instituting such interventions on time, if at all. Against that reality, exchange entitlement-driven urban food

markets which are highly volatile to unstable, erratic food supplies, will predictably respond through price rises³. Increased prices will make food unaffordable, especially for most working class and the urban poor. The destruction of road networks(**Figs 8 and 9**) has in no small way contributed to the non-uniform distribution of food and, in most cases, resulted in food wastage as they could not be transported to the processing plants (Gamble, Sussman, & Wilbanks, 2021).

Fig. 8: Flooded road from the Farm to the market

Fig.9: Road networks destroyed by flood

Another dimension relates to how climate change-linked high and rising temperatures will impact food utilization in urban settings. High temperatures will require food storage and safety techniques that can withstand adverse radiation. Current refrigeration systems are an obvious storage option, but how many urban poor and working class in villages own refrigerators? Their food storage and safety techniques are pressured by current temperatures; hence, increased temperatures can only worsen their plight. High temperatures will also mean perishable food products will have a short shelf life, thus requiring immediate consumption.

Food Security and Pests

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Rising temperatures might also indirectly impact food security through effects on pests, although the interactions between climate and pest incidence are not fully quantified. As the climate warms, it is expected that the range of agricultural pests may expand, as the ability of pest populations to survive the winter and attack susceptible crops increases. Newman (2014) opined that pests, such as aphids and weevil larvae, respond positively to higher carbon dioxide concentrations. Increased temperatures in winter also reduce the mortality of aphids, enabling earlier and potentially larger dispersion (Cotty, & Aime-Garica, 2017).

In Sub-Saharan Africa, evidential research shows that migration patterns of locusts may be influenced by rainfall patterns; therefore, climate change may impact the distribution of this pest ¹⁷. The risk of increased aflatoxin contamination in some areas due to changing rainfall patterns, too, may restrict the area over which certain crops like maize can be grown. Maize is a staple for millions of people in Africa, Asia, and the Americas, but it is susceptible to climate influences as exemplified by recent experiences with aflatoxins in Kenya (Cotty, & aime-Garica, 2017).

Policy and Governmental Response

The Nigerian government has initiated various policies and programs to mitigate the impact of climate change on agriculture and food security.

1. National Climate Change Policy and Response Strategy

The Nigerian government launched the National Adaptation Strategy and Plan of Action on Climate Change (NASPA-CCN) to enhance resilience and adaptive capacity (Federal Ministry of Environment, 2018).

2. Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA)

The ATA aims to modernize agriculture through mechanization, improved seed varieties, and climate-smart agriculture (Adesina, 2014). However, implementation has been slow due to inadequate funding and policy inconsistencies.

3. Green Alternative Agricultural Promotion Policy

This policy emphasizes sustainable farming practices, agroforestry, and water conservation

techniques to combat climate change (Ogundele & Adebisi, 2019).

4. International Partnerships

Nigeria collaborates with international organizations like the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the World Bank to implement climate adaptation programs, such as the Great Green Wall Initiative, aimed at curbing desertification.

Socioeconomic and Cultural Factors

1. Poverty and Limited Resources

Most Nigerian farmers are smallholder farmers with limited financial resources, making it difficult to invest in climate-resilient agriculture (Oladipo, 2020). The high cost of improved seeds, fertilizers, and irrigation facilities prevents many from adopting adaptive strategies.

2. Traditional Agricultural Practices

Cultural attachment to traditional farming techniques hampers the adoption of modern climate-smart agriculture. Awareness campaigns and education are crucial in shifting mindsets (Okeke, 2017).

3. Gender Disparities

Women, who constitute a significant portion of Nigeria's agricultural workforce, often face gender-based discrimination in accessing land, credit, and extension services. Enhancing gender inclusion in climate adaptation programs is necessary (Ogunleye & Akinbode, 2021).

Comparative Analysis

1. Nigeria vs. Other African Countries

Nigeria faces similar climate-related agricultural challenges of other African nations. Ethiopia, for

instance, has successfully implemented large-scale irrigation schemes to mitigate drought effects (FAO, 2022). Nigeria could adopt similar strategies to improve resilience.

2. Nigeria vs. Developed Nations

Countries like the Netherlands and Israel have leveraged technology to develop climate-resilient agriculture, including precision farming and hydroponics. Nigeria can learn from these models by investing in research and development (Akinyemi, 2023).

Conclusion

The impact of climate change on Nigerian agriculture and food security is profound, with erratic weather patterns, rising temperatures, and pest outbreaks threatening livelihoods. While the government has introduced policies and initiatives, challenges such as poor implementation, inadequate funding, and socio-cultural barriers persist. To safeguard food security, Nigeria must strengthen its climate adaptation policies, invest in sustainable agricultural practices, and foster international cooperation. Addressing socioeconomic disparities, enhancing research, and promoting awareness will be crucial in mitigating the long-term effects of climate change on agriculture and food security in Nigeria.

There is an emerging consensus that changes in temperature and precipitation can have detrimental impacts on the food security of the most vulnerable people, in the absence of adaptation. However, the aggregate impact of climate change on food security is not fully understood. In particular, several of the impacts

are difficult to quantify and depend on a range of assumptions. The available quantitative studies suggest that climate change will negatively affect food security at the global level in the long run. The research suggests that, at the global level, climate change will reduce crop yields and the land suitable for agricultural production with the greatest impacts in tropical latitudes where the greatest food security challenges persist.

Several quantitative assessments also suggest that food prices will increase as a result of climate change, thereby affecting the ability of poor farmers to purchase food. The impact of these food price rises will ultimately depend on the level of socioeconomic development: in the shorter term, it is expected that the greatest gains in food access will be in South Asia and Latin America with marginal gains in Sub-Saharan Africa.

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